

Practice Abstract no. 42

Strengthening regulations for data governance and ethical AI use

The #Data4Food Cluster comprising the [DRG4Food](#), [FOODITY](#), [FoodDataQuest](#), and [SOSFood](#) projects organised a joint workshop in June 2025 to discuss challenges, enablers, and gains related to data sharing and AI-driven solutions for sustainable food systems. Two breakout room sessions explored perspectives from both consumers/citizens and industry/food system actors on data sharing and AI in food systems.

Building on the findings of the workshop and breakout room sessions, the following recommendation and driving actions was proposed:

Recommendation: Strengthen regulations for data governance and ethical AI use.

Proposed Actions:

- 1. Revise data protection laws:** Review and adapt existing data protection regulations, informed by feedback collected through a public consultation or other method(s). The objective is two-fold: (1) to reduce complexity for greater accessibility, and (2) to specifically address data issues within the food system, such as data ownership and interoperability.
- 2. Establish ethical AI guidelines for food systems:** Considering AI's growing significance across all sectors, including food systems, it is essential to establish clear ethical guidelines and standards for its development and deployment in the food domain. These guidelines must prioritise accountability and transparency. Such a framework should be developed through a multi-stakeholder process, incorporating input from governmental bodies, academic experts, and representatives from the food industry.
- 3. Establish traceable enforcement mechanisms:** Establishing strong enforcement mechanisms, which are both traceable and capable of holding organisations accountable, is essential once data and AI regulations are developed. These mechanisms are necessary to ensure compliance and allow for the imposition of penalties for non-compliance with established laws.

The aforementioned information is available and further detailed in the joint report developed by the #Data4Food Cluster "What Helps and What Hurts When Sharing Data for Sustainable Food Solutions."

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